

Conference report

Building Bridges

Shaping Europe's science-for-policy landscape

May 26–27, 2025
Vienna, Austria

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Scientific Advice Mechanism
to the European Commission

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Introduction

Building Bridges: Shaping Europe's Science-for-Policy Landscape was a two-day international conference held in Vienna on 26–27 May 2025, organised by SAPEA on behalf of the SAM and hosted by the Austrian Academy of Sciences.

The conference brought together a diverse and high-level group of participants, including scientists, policymakers, science advisors, research funders, communicators, civil society actors, and representatives from European institutions. Its goal was **to explore how scientific evidence and expertise can best support policy making in today's complex, fast-moving, and often polarised policy environment**, and how Europe's science-for-policy ecosystem can be **strengthened and made more resilient** for the future.

Under the theme *Building Bridges*, the event **focused on fostering dialogue and mutual**

understanding between different communities and institutions engaged in science advice.

Participants engaged in a dynamic programme of keynote speeches, expert panels, parallel sessions, and interactive formats that addressed core challenges such as trust in science, the uptake of evidence in decision-making, the impact of AI on scientific processes, and the institutional frameworks that shape science advice across Europe.

The setting in Vienna provided an ideal backdrop for both reflection and forward-looking exchange, and the event served as a space for building new connections, identifying shared goals, and shaping a collective vision for how scientific knowledge can better inform democratic governance.

The event was held in a hybrid format, with 250 participants in person and over 400 joining online.

Check out the two-day event recordings and a two-minute highlight video on our YouTube channel: youtube.com/@EUScienceAdvice

Leonora Harty
Department of Further
& Higher Education,
Research, Innovation &
Science, Ireland

Salomėja Vanagienė
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Scientific Advice Mechanism

to the European Commission

**Building Bridges
Shaping Europe's
science-for-policy
landscape**

Scientific
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ÖAW
ÖSTERBEICHISCHE
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Programme summary

Day 1

Setting the scene

The conference opened with a series of high-level welcome messages that underscored the importance of strengthening Europe's science-for-policy landscape in an era of uncertainty and transformation.

Heinz Fassmann, President of the Austrian Academy of Sciences, and European Commissioner Ekaterina Zaharieva, shared their reflections through recorded messages. Both highlighted the value of science-informed policymaking and the importance of institutional cooperation across Europe.

Representing the host country, Eva-Maria Holzleitner, Austria's Minister of Women, Science, and Research, delivered the opening address in person. Her speech emphasised the role of scientific advice in democratic governance and the need to equip Europe with strong, trusted mechanisms that link evidence to policy. Her presence helped frame the event as a platform for open exchange and collaboration between the scientific and policy communities.

Plenary I Interactive Political Debate

Speakers

- **Barbara Weitgruber**
Director General for Scientific Research, International Relations
- **Nebojša Nakićenović**
(Outgoing) Deputy chair of the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors
- **Ştefan Constantinescu**
Chair of the board of SAPEA
- **Nils-Eric Sahlin**
European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
- **Joanna Drake**
Deputy Director-General of DG-RTD, European Commission

Moderator

- **Jacki Davis**

One of the most anticipated sessions of the conference was the Interactive Political Debate, which brought together prominent figures from the European science-for-policy landscape to discuss the political dimen-

sions of scientific advice and the institutional conditions required for its effective use.

Barbara Weitgruber, Director General at the Austrian Federal Ministry of Women, Science, and Research, opened the discussion by reflecting on Austria's commitment to evidence-informed policymaking and the importance of embedding scientific advice into public institutions.

The panel featured Nebojša Nakićenović, outgoing Deputy Chair of the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors, who shared insights from his tenure and underlined the need for continuity and trust in advisory structures. Stefan Constantinescu, Chair of the SAPEA Board, spoke about the contribution of academies and interdisciplinary science to the advice ecosystem.

From an ethics perspective, Nils-Eric Sahlin of the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies highlighted the importance of balancing scien-

tific knowledge with ethical reflection in decision-making. Joanna Drake, Deputy Director-General of DG-RTD at the European Commission, offered a policy-level view on how the European Commission integrates advice, ethics, and public trust into research and innovation governance.

The discussion was interactive and candid, exploring both achievements and ongoing challenges in strengthening the relationship between science and politics. Participants engaged with audience questions, making the session a dynamic and thoughtful exploration of how science advice operates in real-world policy environments.

Speakers' Key Messages:

Minister Holzleitner's opening word:

There are many principal obstacles that make it difficult to integrate scientific evidence into policy making. A lot of common ground and understanding among stakeholders still needs to be developed. Different national governance systems influence policymaking cultures and practices, and across policy domains, conventions also differ as to what counts as evidence.

The role of a science and research ministry is manifold: we are funders, policymakers, promoters and users of research at the same time. We can enhance the S4P (Science for Policy) readiness of the system for sectoral ministries. We can support interdisciplinary programmes, including social sciences and humanities, and emphasise the need for an excellent, well-funded science

system based on scientific freedom as the fundament for good scientific advice.

In Austria, we will take the ERA Policy Agenda as an opportunity to mobilise actors in the S4P ecosystem with a view to strengthening an overall culture of research and policy engagement. We will join efforts and work towards a common ecosystem by working with line ministries and public administration, parliament, and scientific institutions, as well as science advisory councils.

Joanna Drake

The role of science and ethics advisors is essential for responsible, democratic, and forward-looking policymaking, especially in addressing complex issues like climate change, energy security, and public health crises, but also to bring relevant subjects to the attention of policymakers. Despite challenges—including politicisation, misinforma-

tion, and algorithmic manipulation—advisors must build trust, welcome diverse perspectives, and uphold scientific integrity. To effectively inform policy decisions, advice must be timely, relevant, and communicated clearly, making it accessible to policymakers and the public.

The EU can be a global leader in integrating science and ethics advice into policymaking, benefiting from trusted mechanisms like the Scientific Advice Mechanism and the European Group on Ethics. However, Europe's fragmented science-for-policy ecosystem requires attention. To build visibility, coherence, and robustness, we need sustained investment in both research and a culture of science advice across political leadership and society. Mutual learning, capacity building, and cross-border collaboration are crucial to developing a stronger and more resilient S4P landscape.

Coherent research and innovation policy (R&I) is vital for an effective science-for-policy ecosystem, reinforcing science as a key driver of solutions to global challenges. This approach strengthens Europe's resilience and preparedness for future crises. Continued international collaboration and science diplomacy with willing and like-minded partners are vital to maintain scientific excellence and policy impact. Scientists and policymakers must focus on clear communication, mutual understanding, and trust, ensuring that science advice aligns with policy goals and meets societal expectations.

Nebojša Nakićenović

Bridging Science and Policy: The world is facing a confluence of multiple crises—from violent conflict and economic volatility to inequality and environmental decline—while public trust in science is weakening. Addressing these complex challenges requires science advice that is systemic, interdisciplinary, and holistic. We must break down academic and policy silos to create more effective, integrated and holistic solutions.

Bridging Short-Term Action with Long-Term Vision: Political cycles often prioritise immediate action and gains, but the problems we face demand long-term vision. Science advice should help bridge this gap, guiding decisions that offer both short-term benefits and sustainable outcomes. An example is aligning current actions with the long-term goals of initiatives like the New European Deal.

Reforming Science Advice: Scientific advice itself must evolve. It should be ever more independent, evidence-based, peer-reviewed, transparent, inclusive, and free from self-interest. To be effective, advice must also be succinct, clear and accessible, especially for decisions under conditions of uncertainty, where sound scientific guidance is most critical. This calls for strengthening institutional mechanisms for science advice, promoting deliberative processes, and fostering trust through integrity and openness.

Ștefan Constantinescu

Science has enormously progressed, and a number of issues are well established and verified in the past and in the future. For those issues, many more communication efforts are required for transmitting the safe and unquestionable scientific facts and conclusions to the public, politicians, investors, and other groups. The National Academies of Sciences, Medicine, Engineering, and Humanities; ALLEA; and Academia Europaea are an ideal group to provide this guidance.

There are major problems that are not solved and critical scientific questions and needs that are not yet answered or met. That so many questions are not answered is not an argument to contest what is very well scientifically established. Promises of solutions should not be confused with actual solutions to unanswered scientific questions.

The ability to screen scientifically sound and factual information from non-scientifically sound or fraudulent information needs to be built by education, which will be

Greater role and public participation in policy-making Europe
19th April 2023
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reflected in how the public, politicians, and all societal actors uptake public information and act upon it. The concept of peer review in science needs to be translated to the public by cultivating a critical and analytical spirit and the exigence to have reliable confirmation first before believing any information in the public space. This problem of believing unverified information and taking it as valid information has been a major issue in medicine, and patient experience can be translated to a broader area.

Nils-Eric Sahlin

Policymakers need good-quality science advice but also good-quality ethical advice. Informed decision-making and recommendations are based on knowledge, information, and ethical values, on science and ethics. When knowledge gaps are too large and scientific uncertainties too uncertain, there is every reason to be cautious. There is currently no uniform theory for decision-making under deep uncertainty. This is a problem for policymakers.

Barbara Weitgruber

Scientists and policymakers define problems differently (something to be solved based on scientific methods with a scientific consensus vs. a much more social process of negotiating solutions that have majority support), and the science for policy ecosystem does not only rely on these two legs, namely science and politics, but it also encompasses civil society and public administration.

The duality between the world of science and research and the world of politics and of policy making does not make it impossible to include science in a policy process, but it is not an easy task, nor one to be taken for granted. Besides, not all science automatically becomes evidence for evidence informed policymaking, and the respective roles in the S4P ecosystem need to be understood, and expectations need to be managed.

If advice is not sought or even actively declined, if fields of science and research are declared 'unnecessary' or 'unwanted,' and budgets for these fields are cut, this does not only pose serious threats to knowledge creation, to science and research in general, and to science for policy ecosystems, but also to liberal democracies, especially as we also witness signs of erosion of academic freedom and freedom of scientific research in several countries.

“What we see is that there is an enormous discrepancy between our economy and the economy of the planet. We must go for a reset.”

— Louise Vet

Parallel sessions

Three sessions ran in parallel. Each session was moderated by its organiser.

Parallel session I

Why transformative economic change remains elusive: bridging the gap between science and policy

Organised by **EASAC** and **The Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW)**

Speakers

- **Louise Vet**
Former director of The Netherlands Institute of Ecology and emeritus professor of ecology at Wageningen University
- **Bas Eickhout**
Member of the European Parliament

Moderator

- **Sabine Froning**
EASAC Communications Advisor

Despite decades of scientific evidence highlighting the urgent need for socio-economic transformation, policymakers often struggle to integrate scientific insights into actionable policies. The widening gap between scientific warnings and political decision-making underscores the challenges of leveraging scientific advice to drive meaningful change. In an era of deepening environmental and social crises, the role of science in shaping policy is more critical—and contested—than ever.

The session explored the challenges in translating scientific evidence into policy actions that support sustainable economic and social systems, examined why resistance to transformative change remains strong despite growing recognition of planetary crises, and discussed how scientists can enhance their influence in policy processes to foster systemic transformation.

Session Key Messages

To influence EU policies, we must put more effort into understanding political thinking, cycles, agendas, and needs and adjust the formats and language of our publications. Scientific complexity has its beauty, but so has simplicity: policymakers are looking for clear, actionable recommendations that consider the political priorities of the moment. Crowd intelligence can be a great asset in creating better products and improving acceptance, which is a good reason to make science advice more inclusive and co-creative.

Parallel session II

The great policy debate: national interests vs. global goals

Organisers: **International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, Austrian Academy of Sciences and Finnish Academy of Science and Letters**

Speakers

- **Keywan Riahi**
IIASA Energy, Climate, and Environment Program Director
- **Lena Höglund-Isaksson**
IIASA Pollution Management Research Group Senior Research Scholar

- **Jan Marco Müller**
Team Leader Global Approach,
Multilateral Dialogue, and Science
Diplomacy, European Commission
- **Amani El-Rayes**
Institute of National Planning,
Egypt
- **Alessandro Allegra**
Policy Officer, Science Policy,
Advice and Ethics Unit, European
Commission DG Research
& Innovation
- **Jaakko Kuosmanen**
Academy Secretary, Finnish Acad-
emy of Sciences and Letters

As an international institute addressing complex challenges through multilateral collaborations, IIASA frequently navigates the delicate balance between tackling pressing global and regional issues and informing national policies of its member countries.

In this debate, experts in systems thinking, policymakers, and scientific advisors were assigned opposing positions, either advocating for a global/regional approach or a national approach.

This structured debate format was designed to spark intense conversations, ensure equal representation of both perspectives, and explore how to effectively reconcile global coordination with national priorities in addressing the world's most pressing challenges.

The friendly debate was followed by a fishbowl with open chair discussion, beginning with the debate speakers and inviting audience members to join the conversation, share their experiences, and offer diverse perspectives.

Session Objective

Understanding the dynamics between global, regional, and national interests in policy advice. Informed perspectives on

“In a time of uncertainty, polarisation, and rapid change, Science for Policy offers a way to ground public decisions in shared understanding, not to eliminate debate, but to elevate it.”

— Karen Fabbri

how science can inform policy both locally and globally, emphasising the challenges in providing science-based advice that is both universally applicable and contextually relevant.

Session’s key messages:

Trust in science is declining, making transparency and clear communication essential to rebuild public confidence. To remain impactful, science advice must be tailored to national policy contexts while maintaining global relevance, with careful narrative framing to bridge scientific evidence and societal priorities. Scientists often navigate the dual role of expert and citizen, highlighting the need for structural support and recognition within their institutions, where science advice work is still undervalued and under-incentivized.

Inclusive and effective science advice requires engaging diverse voices, from citizens and indigenous knowledge holders to researchers from low- and middle-income countries, to ensure legitimacy and equity. In an era where science is increasingly intertwined with geopolitics, global frameworks must remain adaptable, collaborative, and inclusive to balance national interests with shared global goals.

Parallel session III

Science advice in a contested world: a case study of solar radiation modification

Organised by SAM.

Speakers

- **Nebojša Nakićenović**
(Outgoing) Deputy Chair of the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors
- **Nils-Eric Sahlin**
European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
- **Aarti Gupta**
Member of the SAPEA Working Group on SRM

This session explored how scientific advisors can offer coherent and balanced guidance on highly contested issues, using the recent work on solar radiation modification as a case study. In response to a 2024 request from the European Commission, the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors, supported by SAPEA's expert group and an ethics statement from the European Group on Ethics, delivered a comprehensive advice package.

The session offered insights into how consensus was built across science, ethics, and policy and highlighted lessons from navigating complexity and controversy in science advice.

Session’s key messages:

Clear, science-based advice on controversial and ethically complex issues is possible when processes are structured, transparent, and inclusive. Diversity in expertise and perspective should be seen as a strength rather than a barrier, as trust and open

dialogue enable the formation of credible, balanced consensus. Collaboration between scientific and ethics bodies (e.g., SAPEA and the European Group on Ethics) enriches the robustness and credibility of the advice provided.

Transparency about disagreements, limitations, and uncertainties helps build legitimacy, particularly in politically sensitive contexts. Lessons from the case of solar radiation modification highlight the value of early engagement and continuous reflection among researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders.

“Strengthening evidence-informed policymaking requires bringing together all relevant stakeholders, which makes it possible to create interaction and shared knowledge.”

— Anne-Greet Keizer

Plenary II

Towards a stronger science-for-policy ecosystem in Europe

Participants in this session from the national level and the European Commission are:

- **Alessandro Allegra**
European Commission
- **Leonora Harty**
Ireland
- **Salomėja Vanagienė**
Lithuania
- **Julia Prikoszovits**
Austria
- **Mariana Hankova**
Czechia
- **Ilkka Tuomi**
Finland
- **Anne-Greet Keizer**
European Commission
- **Karen Fabbri**
European Commission

Moderator

- **Jacki Davis**

This session provided an overview of the European Commission’s ongoing efforts—led by DG RTD, the Joint Research Centre (JRC), and DG REFORM—to strengthen Science for Policy (S4P) across Europe. It featured a presentation of the key findings from the Horizon Europe Policy Support Facility Mutual Learning Exercise (PSF MLE) on Science for Policy, with a particular focus on insights relevant to EU Member States. The session also fostered active dialogue with stakeholders and the wider conference audience, encouraging reflections on national

experiences and lessons learnt. Participating countries were invited to share feedback on their own approaches and planned next steps. In parallel, the session served as a platform for research and innovation actors to discuss priority actions for advancing S4P within the framework of the European Research Area (ERA).

During this session, Karen Fabbri from DG RTD, European Commission, highlighted that on 23 May the EU Council endorsed the new European Research Area (ERA) policy agenda 2025-2027, which puts Science for Policy (S4P) at the centre of EU R&I policy with an action on advancing the European Science for Policy (S4P) Ecosystem. The action aims at (1) improving the cross-cutting integration of knowledge in public policies; (2) strengthening the 'Science for Policy' ecosystem; and (3) promoting collaboration among S4P actors. Its implementation will be supported by a Horizon Europe call under the WIDERA work programme 2025 that aims to foster a more connected, capable, and visible S4P ecosystem by supporting a vibrant community of practice, a network of correspondents in R&I ministries and agencies, and by creating an observatory of the European S4P ecosystem and its practices.

Fabbri added: MLE provided a deeper conceptual understanding of an S4P system. For example, the way in which evidence is created and moves between diverse actors in a complex ecosystem. Generating evidence for policy is not a simple transaction of knowledge demand and supply. Through the MLE, we explored theories related to knowledge management and it helped me to understand that these interactions are rooted in much more social and collaborative processes. Therefore, we need to consider the quality and sustainability of engagement, and to focus on better relationships, collaboration, and cohesion among research/policy actors across the system.

How is this impacting your organisation? Have you been able to use what you learnt to help to mobilise colleagues and to kickstart & drive change? We have shared our experience and the MLE outputs with our networks and stakeholders from both

the policy and research sectors. It has been helpful to reflect on efforts to drive the development of S4P within participant countries and advocate for it at the national level.

There have been significant developments in Ireland over the last year, which will help to support the S4P agenda. We have a new funding agency (Research Ireland), which is better positioned to fund multidisciplinary policy challenges and whose functions under a new Research & Innovation Act 2024 include the undertaking of research to inform the development of public policy. We also have appointed a government science advisor, which is a new role focused on supporting science advice to the government. Insights into S4P activity and good practice across EU counterparts through the MLE network came at a critical time.

What is needed at the systems level, and how can all those with a part to play best work together to deliver that change? Continuing to drive this ecosystem approach and reduce fragmentation is the key challenge. The MLE has been hugely informative and key to making connections with colleagues and agreement on common principles/concepts. However, we should work to maintain and expand these connections and capitalise on these efforts. At a national level, we are committed to building on our learning and maintaining this connectivity through the forthcoming TSI and ERA programs.

Saloméja Vanagienė

The MLE was an experience where you understand that you are not alone on the evidence-informed policymaking road. I learnt that in Europe and in the world, we have a lot of different pathways to achieve the goal for Evidence-Informed Policymaking (EIPM). I learnt that first of all, you need to understand the environment where you want to foster EIPM and then start with small steps, which can be the discussion about the need for the systems and establishing some positions that help to keep the way.

Second, I learnt that we need to share the experience. That helps to understand what I am writing or what I should change to have better results. And personally, I gain understanding of evaluation criteria and needs. It is hard to say what the impact is in our country, but thanks to this MLE, we share ideas from other countries with our communities and help them to understand what S4P is.

Julia Prikozovits

It changed how I think about S4P in such a way that I understood that this is a systems endeavour where we need to navigate with multiple stakeholder communities, their expertise, and their interests. The MLE was very useful in terms of showcasing that S4P ecosystems in Europe are collectively in transition and are being recalibrated.

The MLE prepared the ground for the institutional commitment needed to improve the Austrian S4P ecosystem. Austria will now endeavour on the follow-up of the ERA Policy Agenda by establishing a national ERA Action Plan, which will also include the further development of our S4P ecosystem.

I think we do need some more reflection collectively in Europe as to what we want the system to change exactly and what good performance of an S4P ecosystem actually means. What we have in mind with driving EIPM and S4P forward is a change of political and scientific styles and culture. It is important to keep the momentum going and to stay in contact.

Mariana Hankova

MLE gave me perspective and reassurance. Many of the challenges we face in Czechia are not unique, they are systemic and widely

shared. Seeing how others are addressing them gives us hope and a sense of direction. MLE reminded us of the broader scope of S4P. It's not just about improving individual interactions but also keeping in mind the complexity it entails. It reinforced and legitimised our reform agenda. In particular, it highlighted the importance of intermediaries and safe spaces.

Anne-Greet Keizer

An evidence-informed policymaking ecosystem does not self-organise, even in countries with advanced systems of governance. Some form of coordination is necessary to make sure the different elements of the ecosystem talk to each other. Strengthening evidence-informed policymaking requires bringing together all relevant stakeholders, which makes it possible to create interaction and shared knowledge.

Karen Fabbri

In a time of uncertainty, polarisation, and rapid change, Science for Policy (S4P) offers a way to ground public decisions in shared understanding, not to eliminate debate, but to elevate it. Aware of this, the EU has placed S4P at the heart of its research and innovation agenda, with the Council's endorsement of the European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda 2025–2027 and its dedicated action on advancing the European S4P Ecosystem. This reflects a strong commitment to improving the integration of scientific knowledge into public policymaking across sectors.

The action focuses on three core objectives: enhancing the cross-cutting use of knowledge in policy, strengthening the S4P ecosystem, and promoting collaboration among S4P actors. To achieve this, it will support a Community of Practice open to all S4P stakeholders, establish a Network of S4P correspondents from national R&I ministries and agencies, and set up an Observatory to map practices, identify needs, and share tools and resources.

A Horizon Europe WIDERA 2025 call will support the implementation of this action, by funding a consortium of S4P actors, which will animate and serve as the secretariat of the Community of Practice, creating the enabling conditions for efficient mutual learning and collaboration. The aim is to foster a more connected, capable, and visible S4P ecosystem across Europe.

“Political cycles often prioritise immediate action and gains, but the problems we face demand long-term vision. Science advice should help bridge this gap, guiding decisions that offer both short-term benefits and sustainable outcomes.”

— Nebojša Nakićenović

Ideas market

The first day culminated in a dynamic Ideas Market, an informal networking hub where participants connected, shared insights, and explored collaborative opportunities. Contributors presented their initiatives through academic-style poster displays, each showcasing innovative strategies for strengthening Europe's science-for-policy landscape.

The foundation for these evening exchanges was laid earlier during a rapid-fire pitch session following the second plenary. Each Ideas Market participant delivered a compelling 60-second overview of their work to the full assembly, creating anticipation and identifying potential synergies for deeper exploration.

This dual format (brief presentations followed by extended poster conversations) fostered meaningful cross-disciplinary dialogue in an accessible, energizing environment that balanced academic rigor with genuine human connection.

Programme summary

Day 2

“Engaging and empowering young scientists across disciplines at the critical intersection of science, policy, and diplomacy today can transform the science advice landscape of tomorrow.”

— Jovana Milic

Storytelling talk

Juan Lucas Restrepo

- **Juan Lucas Restrepo**
Director General of the Alliance of Bioversity International and CIAT (CGIAR)

The second day of the conference began with a welcome coffee, offering participants a chance to reconnect and ease into the morning discussions. The programme opened with an inspiring storytelling talk by Juan Lucas Restrepo, Director General of the Alliance of Bioversity International and CIAT (CGIAR). Drawing on his extensive experience in global science-policy cooperation, he shared personal insights and reflections on the power of narrative in shaping more inclusive, impactful science-for-policy ecosystems.

Juan Lucas Restrepo shared reflections from his roles in policy and science, highlighting the power of trust-based, long-term collaboration between scientists and policymakers. He emphasised the value of interdisciplinary work and context-specific solutions to global challenges.

Challenges include misaligned incentives, disconnects between science and local needs, and gaps in mutual understanding between science and policy. Restrepo called for more co-designed approaches, ongoing dialogue, and institutional spaces that support evidence-based, inclusive decision-making.

Parallel sessions

Parallel session IV

Bridging the gap: Universities and municipalities co-producing solutions for urban transformation

Hosted by University of Granada, École Nationale Supérieure d'Architecture de Paris-La Villette, University of Aveiro, Graz University, University of Vic - Central University of Catalonia (UVic-UCC), Ca' Foscari University of Venice, Palacký University Olomouc, Tiber Umbria Comett Education Programme, Agrupación de Profesionales para el Desarrollo Internacional

Speakers

- **Esteban Romero-Frías**
University of Granada
- **Holger Hoff**
Graz University
- **José Carlos Mota**
University of Aveiro
- **Ada Domingo Ferrer**
University of Vic—Central University of Catalonia
- **Stefano Campostrini**
Ca' Foscari University of Venice
- **Jakub Konicek**
Palacký University Olomouc
- **Maria Brizi**
Tiber Umbria Comett Education Programme
- **Encarnación Lorente García**
APDI Group

An interactive session exploring innovative approaches and science-policy mechanisms to connect universities and municipalities, drawing on practical examples to address urban challenges like socio-economic development, inequality, depopulation or overpopulation, digital transformation, and climate change.

This session addressed opportunities for connecting universities and their regions, mainly through municipalities, to foster science-policy dialogues and co-development of solutions for complex urban challenges. The session explored how inter- and trans-disciplinary collaboration and participatory methodologies can bridge institutional gaps and catalyse joint action for urban agendas.

Session's key messages:

To build lasting partnerships, universities and local governments should formalise strategic alliances that ensure continuity and shared commitment over time. These alliances help establish stable relationships that go beyond short-term initiatives and foster trust between institutions.

Effective territorial solutions require mixed forums where municipalities, academia, and civil society come together to identify local challenges and set priorities. Living Labs can serve as powerful engines of transformation when they actively engage citizens, companies, and researchers in co-creating and testing innovative responses that address real community needs.

European funding achieves greater impact when projects are closely aligned with local development agendas and strategies, ensuring that investments directly support the priorities and long-term vision of each territory. Citizen science also plays a key role in democratising knowledge, enabling people to become active contributors to research and policy design rather than passive recipients.

Finally, providing scientific advice at the local level requires dedicated mechanisms that make academic expertise accessible, timely, and relevant for local administrations. Building transnational

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networks of universities committed to local transformation strengthens collective capacity and fosters mutual learning. A strong, shared narrative that positions universities as drivers of social cohesion and sustainability further enhances their legitimacy and broadens public support.

Parallel session V

Making the Case: Forward-looking Science–Policy–Society Interfaces for Tackling Nexus Challenges across Scales, Sectors, and Actors

Co-organised by: **Montpellier Process, BioAgora, INRAE**

Speakers

- **Fabrice De Clerck**
CGIAR
- **Sélim Louafi**
CIRAD
- **Marie Vandewalle**
BioAgora
- **Nils Ferrand**
INRAE
- **Amanda Harding**
Convène
- **Karen Fabbri**
European Commission

An interactive dialogue spotlighting forward-looking models for science–policy–society interfaces operating across the feed–care–protect nexus that mobilise collective intelligence to address interconnected challenges across sectors, scales, and actors. Drawing on real-world initiatives,

this session explored practical tensions and opportunities in designing impactful, inclusive, and adaptive SPIs.

This session contributed to the SAM Conference theme Science Advice in Politics and Society by bringing together diverse experiences from the Montpellier Process, BioAgora, and INRAE. It explored the persistent question: why invest in interfacing when it's so difficult, and what's at stake if we don't? Through participatory formats, including directive fishbowls and live sensemaking, the session co-developed insights into overcoming institutional lock-ins, identifying actionable paths toward more effective, equitable, and impactful science-policy interfaces.

Session's key messages:

Science–Policy–Society Interfaces are not self-organised. They require careful design to recognise divergence and move to alignment and action. Rather than smoothing over differences, effective SPSIs create risky-safe spaces that surface disagreement as a starting point for deeper alignment. Real transformation hinges not on technical fixes, but on navigating value-based, political, and systemic tensions with humility and purpose.

Future-fit SPSIs rely on collective intelligence and iterative engagement across all scales. Effective interfaces don't trickle down. They are co-constructed across levels and actors, recognising that

“Young scientists challenge established views and bring innovative perspectives to the table, thereby strengthening the robustness of scientific advice.”

— Jan Marco Müller

cities, communities, and often-overlooked actors (farmers, Indigenous Peoples, and youth) are not just stakeholders but system shapers. Strengthening these ecosystems is key to connecting local traction with global transformation.

The conventional role of science, knowledge, and expertise needs to be revisited. We need a new narrative where the role of science is not only to provide evidence but also to produce knowledge that engages with and informs transformation, is inclusive of diverse knowledge systems, and proposes ways to navigate tensions and trade-offs.

“To build visibility, coherence, and robustness, we need sustained investment in both research and a culture of science advice across political leadership and society.”

— Joanna Drake

Parallel session VI

Unlocking Science Advice—Building Skills and Practices for Young Scientists in Europe

Organisers & Chairs: **International Science Council (ISC)** and the **International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA)**

Speakers

- **Jan Marco Müller**
European Commission
- **Marie Franquin**
IIASA
- **Jovana Milic**
Swiss Young Academy and Global Young Academy
- **Mostafa Moonir Shawrav**
Marie Curie Alumni Association
- **Helen Eenmaa**
Young Academies Science Advice Structure
- **Keri Wong**
UK Young Academy

An interactive session explored innovative approaches and science–policy mechanisms to connect universities and municipalities, drawing on practical examples to address urban challenges such as socio-economic development, inequality, depopulation or overpopulation, digital transformation, and climate change.

This session addressed opportunities for connecting universities and their regions, mainly through municipalities, to foster science–policy dialogues and co-development

of solutions for complex urban challenges. It explored how inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration and participatory methodologies could bridge institutional gaps and catalyse joint action for urban agendas.

Speaker Quotes

Jan Marco Müller

"Young scientists challenge established views and bring innovative perspectives to the table, thereby strengthening the robustness of scientific advice."

Marie Franquin

"If you're starting out in science policy, don't wait to build connections, raise your profile, or share your work. Strong relationships and a clear voice help you find opportunities and make a real difference."

Jovana Milic

"Engaging and empowering young scientists across disciplines at the critical intersection of science, policy, and diplomacy today can transform the science advice landscape of tomorrow."

Session's key messages:

Building the skills and confidence of early- and mid-career researchers is essential to empower the next generation of Emerging Science Advisors. By fostering meaningful connections and dialogue between emerging researchers and experienced advisors, we strengthen science-policy networks and create lasting pathways for collaboration. Supporting researchers in translating their knowledge into policy-relevant insights, through real-world examples and interactive dialogue, is at the heart of turning science into action.

Final session

Fishbowl Reflections and Closing

Moderator

◆ **Jacki Davis**

The final session of the conference adopted a fishbowl format, creating an open and dynamic space for reflection. This interactive setup allowed participants to step forward, share their impressions, and engage in an informal dialogue about the themes and insights that emerged over the two days. It provided a unique opportunity to connect in-

dividual experiences with the broader objectives of the event, reinforcing the collective spirit of collaboration and learning

To enrich the discussion, rapporteurs from each of the parallel sessions were invited to join the fishbowl and share highlights from their respective sessions. They offered brief summaries of key insights, challenges raised, and takeaways that emerged from the diverse discussions. Their contributions helped to weave together the multiple strands of the programme and ensured that voices from across the conference were reflected in the closing moments.

The session concluded with formal remarks from three distinguished speakers:

- **Nebojša Nakićenović**
Outgoing Deputy Chair of the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors
- **Stefan Constantinescu**
Chair of the Board of SAPEA
- **Nils-Eric Sahlin**
Member of the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies

Each reflected on the importance of strengthening the science–policy interface in Europe, acknowledging both the successes of the conference and the ongoing need for institutional support, cross-sector dialogue, and shared ownership of the challenges ahead. Their closing messages emphasised trust, inclusiveness, and sustained engagement as essential pillars for shaping a resilient, evidence-informed future.

The reflections marked a fitting end to a highly interactive and forward-looking event that brought together a wide range of voices to collectively envision the future of science for policy in Europe.

Side events

Several of our partners and collaborators organised independent side events in connection with the Building Bridges conference. Participation in these side events was open to all, including those who were not registered for the main conference, ensuring broader access and fostering a wider exchange of ideas beyond the core programme.

Side event I

Science advice at a time of crisis: Are we better prepared, or is more still to be done?

13 May 2025, 15:00

In partnership with: **Academia Europaea, Universities Policy Engagement Network**

Speakers

- **Sarah Chaytor**
- **Alessandro Allegra**
- **Pearl Dykstra**
- **Cornel Hart**
- **David Phipps**

The first half of the 2020s has been marked by unprecedented challenges, from the global COVID-19 pandemic and armed conflicts to widespread political and economic uncertainty, alongside the intensifying effects of climate change. These crises have tested the resilience and responsiveness of science advice mechanisms at national and international levels.

This webinar explored key lessons learnt from recent crises, examining how science advisory systems have responded and identifying what improvements are needed to enhance the effectiveness of science advice infrastructures, processes, and practices for the future.

The session was held as a publicly accessible side event to the Scientific Advice Mechanism (SAM) conference.

Side event II

Shaping the European framework for science diplomacy: What is in it for science advice?

26 May 2025, 10:00

In partnership with: Austrian Ministry for European and International Affairs, EU Science Diplomacy Alliance, DLR Projektträger, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, and University of Bergen

Speakers

- Jan Marco Müller
- Arnold Obermayr
- Carolina Cañibano
- Lise Øvreås
- Maria Rentetzi
- Georg Kilzer
- Stella Reschke
- Angela Schindler-Daniels

This side event presented key recommendations from the EU Science Diplomacy Working Group on enhancing the strategic use of scientific evidence in European diplomacy. It marked the culmination of a major co-creation effort launched by the European Commission in 2024.

The session also featured an interactive World Café, where participants explored future scenarios for science advice in foreign and security policy by 2035, focusing on resilience in the face of disruption.

Side event III

Partnering for progress: Strengthening science and policy through multilateral collaboration for tomorrow.

27 May 2025, 14:00

In partnership with: ÖAW, EASAC, and IIASA

Speakers

- Simone Gingrich
- Karen Lips
- Lise Øvreås
- Barbara Weitgruber

This side event explored the growing role of collaborative frameworks in advancing science and shaping effective science advice for policy. Drawing on insights from government representatives and leading institutions, the session highlighted how cross-border, cross-sector, and interdisciplinary partnerships can bridge the gap between science and decision-making.

The event concluded with a networking session featuring around 20 experts from the Austrian Academy of Sciences (ÖAW), the European Academies' Science Advisory Council (EASAC), and the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA). Through informal discussions, poster presentations, and a reception, participants shared case studies of successful multilateral partnerships that have made tangible impacts on policy and society.

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IDEAS MARKET

Most effective idea

Most innovative idea

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ÖAW

Speakers and participants

Speakers

The event attracted a diverse group of distinguished international speakers. A significant number were present in person, while others joined online, reflecting the hybrid nature of the conference. Particular attention was paid to achieving gender balance, resulting in a well-represented mix of women and men among the speakers. In addition, the programme actively included the voices of early-career researchers, with several speakers representing Young Academies across Europe.

The speaker lineup featured high-level representatives from European institutions, national academies, research organisations, and advisory bodies. Most speakers held senior leadership roles within their respective organisations, underlining the high-level nature of the discussions and the strategic importance of the topics addressed.

Participants

A total of 250 participants attended the event in person at the venue. Additionally, the plenary session livestreams on YouTube have collectively received about 600 views to date.

Among the on-site participants were several policymakers, including senior staff from the Austrian ministry of women, science, and research. The audience also included numerous representatives from various academies, universities, and research institutes. In addition, students and members of civil society organisations were present, contributing to a diverse and engaged audience.

The event brought together a highly diverse and international group of participants, representing a wide array of institutions and professional backgrounds. Attendees came from national academies of science, universities, and leading research institutes across Europe. Their fields spanned natural and life sciences, social sciences, engineering, environmental research, and public health, reflecting a deeply interdisciplinary community committed to strengthening the science-policy interface.

Key European institutions were also present, alongside members of national governments. These institutions brought crucial policy perspectives and signalled growing institutional engagement with science diplomacy and evidence-informed policymaking.

In addition to public institutions, a range of civil society organisations, non-profits, think tanks, and international research networks took part. These included science diplomacy platforms, sustainability-focused initiatives, development organisations, and science communication actors.

Overall, the variety of institutions and domains represented, from university leadership to early-career researchers, showed a shared recognition of the value of scientific collaboration across borders and sectors. The event served as a living community, highlighting the importance of fostering inclusive, knowledge-based dialogue to inform European and global decision-making in an increasingly complex and interconnected world. It marked a significant step forward in building and strengthening the science-for-policy community across the EU, supporting efforts to enhance collaboration and impact at all levels.

WHAT DO WE NEED TO DO

Valid Information

Create CULTURE

BUILD RESILIENCE

ADVISE

Collaborate

About Scientific Advice Mechanism (SAM)

The Scientific Advice Mechanism provides independent scientific evidence and policy recommendations to the College of European Commissioners on any subject, including on policy issues that the European Parliament and the Council consider to be of major importance.

We consist of three parts:

- **The Group of Chief Scientific Advisors**, seven eminent scientists whose role is to make policy recommendations
- **SAPEA** (Science Advice for Policy by European Academies), which brings together Europe's academies and Academy Networks to review and synthesise evidence
- **The SAM secretariat**, a unit within the European Commission whose role is to support the Advisors and liaise between the Scientific Advice Mechanism and the European Commission

In some activities, such as communicating about our work, the three parts collaborate closely. But when we give scientific advice, SAPEA and the Advisors work independently, following specific procedures to maintain the independence and quality of our advice.

We also work to raise awareness of scientific advice and evidence in policy making and to stimulate debate in Europe about these issues.

Throughout this website, you can read more about these three parts and how they work: scientificadvice.eu

Follow **@EUScienceAdvice** on social media platforms for more updates:

- LinkedIn**
- Bluesky**
- Twitter/X**
- YouTube**

And don't miss exclusive insights in our **Science for Policy** podcast.

About this Report

This report captures the key discussions, insights, and messages from Building Bridges: Shaping Europe's Science-for-Policy Landscape, a two-day international conference held in Vienna on 26–27 May 2025. Organised by SAPEA on behalf of the European Commission's Scientific Advice Mechanism and hosted by the Austrian Academy of Sciences, the event brought together scientists, policymakers, advisors, communicators, and representatives from civil society and European institutions.

The report provides a detailed overview of the sessions, debates, and exchanges that took place, from high-level plenaries and interactive debates to parallel sessions, workshops, and side events. It is designed to share the lessons learned, highlight best practices, and inspire further dialogue on how to build a stronger, more inclusive, and resilient science-for-policy ecosystem in Europe.

Whether you attended the event or are exploring its outcomes for the first time, this report offers a valuable resource for anyone interested in strengthening the role of evidence in policymaking.

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